

NITROGEN, PHOSPHORUS CONTENT AND UPTAKE WITH THEIR INTERACTIVE EFFECT ON CHICKPEA (*Cicer arietinum* L.) AS INFLUENCED BY DIFFERENT LIQUID BIOFERTILIZERS UNDER VARYING FERTILITY LEVELS**M Prakash Prajapat¹, Surendra Singh² and Lala Ram Yadav³**¹Ph.D. Agronomy, Rajasthan Agricultural Research Institute, Durgapura, SKNAU, Jobner, Rajasthan, India²Dean, College of Agriculture, Kotputali, SKNAU, Jobner, Rajasthan, India³Head, Department of Agronomy, SKNAU, Jobner, Rajasthan, Indiaomprakashagro10@gmail.com

(MS Received: 06.06.2023; MS Revised: 17.07.2023; MS Accepted: 18.07.2023)

MS 3072

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRONOMY,)

Abstract

Chickpeas are a significant source of protein and have the unique ability to maintain and restore soil fertility through biological nitrogen fixation. Nitrogen (N) and Phosphorus (P) are essential mineral constituents for crop growth and vital physiological processes in pulses. However, Phosphorus availability in cereals is limited for numerous reasons. In the case of nitrogen, its high loss potential is due to its highly volatile nature. Therefore, enhancing the bioavailability of nitrogen and phosphorus will assist in improving the production of pulses. A field experiment was conducted in winter (rabi) 2015-16 and 2016-17 at the crop research farm of the Rajasthan agricultural research institute in Durgapura, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India to investigate the effect of liquid biofertilizers under varying fertility levels on nitrogen and phosphorus content and uptake in seed and straw, as well as their interactive effect. The experiment consisted of 28 treatment combinations, comprising of four level of fertility levels, i.e. (control, 50%N + 75%K₂O + 75%P₂O₅ + 75%N + 85%P₂O₅ + 50%S + 100% NPKS 85%K₂O and 75S%) and seven liquid biofertilizer combinations (control, Rhizobium, PSB+PMM (P-Solubilizer & Mobilizer), KMB (K-Mobilizer), Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB, SSB (S-solubilizer) and Rhizobium + PSB + KMB + PMM + SSB) was laid out in split plot design with three replication. Results indicate that 100% NPKS and Rhizobium + PSB + KMB + PMM + SSB have the highest N, P content and assimilation in seed and straw.

Keyword: Nitrogen, phosphorus, content, uptake liquid biofertilizers and fertility levels

Introduction

Pulse crops are significant to India's agricultural economy. An essential component of the largely vegetarian Indian cuisine is pulses. Although pulses, the primary source of vegetable protein in the human diet, are added to cereals, which are a staple meal and the primary energy source, a nutritionally balanced diet is produced. On a dry seed basis, pulses typically contain 21% protein, 2.5–3.0 times higher than cereals. Due to their high protein content (17–23%) and an excellent supply of minerals, carbs, and trace elements, chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) plays a significant role in human nutrition (Namvar et al., 2011). It is a cheap source of high-quality protein for millions of people in developing countries who can't afford animal protein for a healthy diet (Zia Ul-Haq et al., 2007). It plays a big part in farming systems and is utilized as livestock feed (Singh, 1997). The most significant pulse crop in India is the chickpea, which covers 10.56 million hectares and produces 11.23 million tonnes, or 32.21% and 44.51%, respectively, of all pulse areas and production (Anonymous, 2018).

The ability of pulse crops to fix atmospheric nitrogen in symbiotic association with *Rhizobium* makes them vital, if not difficult to replace. This ability is a key factor in the agricultural economy of India. Every pulse plant functions as a little fertilizer factory by significantly contributing to the soil's organic nitrogen enrichment. This gives them an edge over chemical fertilizers, which lose their effectiveness due to ammonia emission during nutrient leaching. The deep penetrating root system of pulse crops is their second distinctive quality. This trait allows them to use the low moisture available more effectively than other crops, including cereals, and also significantly contributes to the loosening of the surface soil. Third, because of their high-quality protein content, which ranges from 20 to 25% and is three times that of cereals, pulses have played a significant role in human diets as a rich source of protein. The biological value of a diet high in cereals and low in pulses is greater than that of either component consumed alone.

Regarding agricultural nutrients, nitrogen and phosphorus are crucial for boosting crop output. Additionally, nitrogenous chemical fertilizers are produced using non-renewable petroleum fuels at high pressures and temperatures. The daily rise in the price of petroleum impacts the cost of chemical fertilizers. Conversely, when more significant quantities of chemical fertilizers are utilized in cultivation to boost output, as it eliminates the helpful bacteria and other elements, it pollutes the ecosystem and is poisonous to the soil. However, plants' growth and metabolism depend heavily on plant

nutrients like N and P. It has also been demonstrated that plants require regular replenishment because modern intensive farming practices cause them to extract more nutrients from the soil. Microbial organisms provide an excellent option to supply the necessary missing nutrients.

These bio-fertilizers are microbial inoculants that contain active microorganisms that effectively fix atmospheric nitrogen, either in symbiosis with the host plant or free-livingly. P₂O₅ is released or mobilized from the soil by phosphate solubilizing or mobilizing microorganisms. Both a liquid form and a powder form of these bio-fertilizers are sold in the market.

Liquid bio-fertilizers are special liquid mixtures that contain not only the necessary microbes and their food but also unique cell protectants, or compounds, that encourage the formation of dormant spores or cysts for longer shelf life and more resistance to bad conditions (Chandra et al., 2006).

Material and method

During the winter (rabi) seasons of 2015–16 and 2016–17 a field experiment was conducted in the Rajasthan Agricultural Research Institute, Durgapura, Sri Karan Narendra Agriculture University, Jobner, Jaipur (75°47' E, 26°51' N, 390 m above sea level). This area belongs to Rajasthan's agroclimatic zone IIIa (the semi-arid eastern plain zone). The typical semi-arid climate of this area is characterized by an arid environment and extreme summer and winter temperatures (4°C and 45.5°C, respectively). It rains on average between 500 and 700 mm. The trial field's soil was loamy sand, somewhat alkaline, low in organic carbon, low in nitrogen (136.4 kg/ha), high in phosphorus (34 kg/ha), and low in potassium (195.4 kg/ha). The experiment comprises four levels of fertility (control, 50%N + 75%P₂O₅ + 75%K₂O + 50%S, 75%N + 75S% + 85%K₂O + 85%P₂O₅ and 100% NPKS) and seven liquid biofertilizer combinations (control, Rhizobium, PSB+PMM (P-Solubilizer & Mobilizer), KMB (K-Mobilizer), Rhizobium + PSB + KMB + PMM, SSB (S-solubilizer) and Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + SSB + KMB) was laid out in split plot design with three replication. The fertilizers used are the ammonium phosphate, urea, muriate of potash, and microsulfur. In addition to the full doses of fertilizers provided basally at the time of sowing, 5 g/kg-1 of carbendazim 50% WP was applied to the seed to protect it from soil- and seed-borne fungi. Using a seed rate of 80 kg ha⁻¹, the seed was manually sown (Kera method) by labour at a depth of roughly 8 cm in rows spaced 30 cm apart. Utilizing the chick-basin system, irrigation was provided according to the crop's needs.

The typical grain and stover samples collected during threshing and winnowing were pulverized, and the nitrogen and phosphorus content was examined.

Nitrogen: Sulfuric acid digestion was used to remove the black color, and hydrogen peroxide was used to calculate the amount of nitrogen present. Nessler's reagent was used to develop colour for the colourimetric method to estimate nitrogen (Snell and Snell, 1949). Calculated nitrogen content was represented as a percentage.

Phosphorus: The amount of phosphorus in grain and stover was quantified using a spectrophotometer after plant samples were digested with di-acid and developed colour with vanadium-molybdate for the colourimetric estimate (Jackson, 1973).

The following relationship was used to estimate the absorption of nitrogen and phosphorus in grain and straw following harvest:

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in grain (\%)} \times \text{Grain yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)} + \text{Nutrient content in stover (\%)} \times \text{Stover yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)}}{100}$$

The results were statistically evaluated per Panse and Sukhatme's (1985) instructions to determine the significance of variance in experimental data collected for different treatment effects.

Result And Discussion

Fertility levels response

The treatment of 100% NPKS in seed and straw (Table 1) produced the highest nitrogen and phosphorus content (percent), which was noticeably comparable to the treatment of 75%N + 85%P₂O₅ + 85%K₂O + 75S%. The nitrogen concentration of treatment 100% NPKS is greater than control treatment, at 6.82% in seed and 6.79% in straw. The phosphorus concentration of 100% NPKS is greater than the control treatment at 6.05% in seed and 8.25% in straw. In addition, 100% NPKS treatment in seed and straw resulted in the maximum N and P uptake (kg ha⁻¹) but was statistically comparable to 75%N + 85%P₂O₅ + 85%K₂O + 75S%. In comparison to control, 100% NPKS treatment enhanced N uptake by 47.61% in seed and 47.21% in straw and increased P uptake by 46.75% in seed and 48.91% in straw. The capacity of the soil mainly determines the amount of nutrients in seed and straw, but it can be changed by adding a specific nutrient we want. N and P are applied to crops gradually, which causes their buildup in the soil and plants. However, their utility begins to drop beyond a certain point, and occasionally adverse effects are visible in the crops. Increased nitrogen content and uptake may be attributable to a greater initial fertilizer supply, which may have improved microbial population, which fixed atmospheric nitrogen and stored it in nodules of crop roots for later use by the plant. Both Patel et al. (2014) and Jat and Ahlawat (2004) found similar results. Phosphorus application may have altered the nutrient environment in the rhizosphere as weandplant system, increasing nutrient uptake and translocation, particularly N and P. The overall intake of N and P was significantly increased by the enormous rise in the concentration of these nutrients as well as the improved seed and straw yield (Kumawat et al. 2009).

Biofertilizers response

The maximum N and P content (%) of biological fertilizers in seed and straw were obtained by Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB + SSB (Table 2), which was comparable to Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB in straw alone. Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB + SSB raised the N content in seed and straw by 5.84% and 2.99%, respectively, over controls. It also increased the P content by 4.93% and 7.27% over controls. Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB + SSB was the biofertilizer combination that recorded the highest N and P uptake by seed and straw. In seed and straw, the uptake of N increased by 38.51 and 34.03 percent, while P uptake increased by 37.21 and 39.51 percent. This may be the result of the work of beneficial microorganisms, which perform such functions as nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilization and mineralization, the release of plant growth regulator, antibiotic production, and the biodegradation of

organic matter, among many others, to keep the soil environment rich in all micro- and macronutrients. This result is consistent with Sinha et al. (2010). Biofertilizers that fix atmospheric nitrogen (N) for use by plants in the soil thereby boosted the available supply of nitrogen. The phosphate-solubilizing bacteria increased the plant's access to phosphate, which may have led to increased nodulation and root growth, which in turn led to higher nodule nitrogen fixation in the soil. Thus, greater uptake by plants and a consequent rise in their concentration in plants resulted from increased availability of nitrogen, phosphorus, and other crucial plant nutrients. Increased concentrations of these nutrients in either seed, straw, or both may cause a significant quantity of N and P uptake by plants. These results are accurate according to Singh and Kapoor (1992) and Singh and Pareek (2003).

Fertility levels and biofertilizers combine the response

Interaction effects (Tables 2 and 3) showed that Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB + SSB and 100% NPKS had the maximum N uptake in seed and straw, respectively. Phosphorus interaction outcomes were best when combined with 100% NPKS and Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB + SSB. This outcome may result from the combined effects of liquid biofertilizer and the recommended fertilizer dosage. Due to the ability of biofertilizer bacteria to transform phosphate from an unavailable state to an available form that plants may utilize. After 50 to 55 DAS, nitrogen-fixing bacteria begin to fix atmospheric nitrogen. Therefore, the starter fertilizer dose used when planting addresses this nutrient shortage phase. Chemical fertilizer and liquid biofertilizer combined effects enabled plants to absorb more N and P. According to Franco et al. (2004), the formation of inorganic polyphosphate, which is encouraged by the addition of carbon elegant, rose due to the increased total N absorption, which in turn enhanced the P availability in the soil. Since nitrate reductase is a crucial component of amino acids, the basic units of protein synthesis, the higher nitrogen concentration may also be explained by increased activity of this enzyme. These results are very similar to those of Yadav O. S. (2003). Phosphorus's importance in photosynthesis and glucose metabolism in leaves is cited as a major limiting element in plant growth by Giaquinta R. T. and B. Quebedeaux (1980). During this phase, phosphorus levels control the ratio of starch to sugar in the source leaves and reproductive organs.

Conclusion

The 100% NPKS and application of biofertilizers (NPK&S) treatment may be recommended as the best treatment in this study based on the results of several quantitative and qualitative features of chickpea, such as Nitrogen and phosphorus content and absorption components. This therapy could be employed in agroecosystems for sustainable agriculture because it appears economical and environmentally responsible.

Acknowledgement

The technical and financial support facilitated by Sri Karan Narendra Agriculture University, Jobner, for conducting research is duly acknowledged.

Discloser statement

The author reports that there are no competing interests to declare.

References

1. **Namvar ali, Sharifi, R.S. and Khandan, T. 2011.** Growth analysis and yield of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) in relation to organic and inorganic nitrogen fertilization. *EKOLOGIA* 57(3): 97-108.
2. **Zia Ul-Haq, M., Iqbal, S., Ahmad, S., Imran, M., Niaz, A. and Bhangar, M.I. 2007.** Nutritional and compositional study of desi chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) cultivars grown in Punjab, Pakistan. *Food Chemistry* 105: 1357-1363.
3. **Singh, K.B. 1997.** Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). *Field Crops Research* 53: 161-170.
4. **Anonymous, 2018.** Agriculture Statistics Department of Statistics and Cooperation, Government of India.

5. **Chandra, K., Greep, S., Ravindranath, P. and Srivathsa, R.S.H. 2006.** Regional Director, Regional Centre of Organic Farming No. 34 5th Main road Hebbal, Banglaore -560024.
6. **Snell, F.B. and Snell, C.T. 1949.** Colorimetric method of analysis. IAD Vannostrand Co., New Delhi.
7. **Jackson, M.L. 1973.** Soil Chemical Analysis. Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
8. **Panse, V.G. and Sukhatme, P.V. 1985.** Statistical methods for agricultural workers. Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi.
9. **Jat, R.S. and Ahalawat, I.P.S. 2004.** Effect of vermicompost, biofertilizers and phosphorus on growth, yield and nutrient uptake by gram (*Cicer arietinum* L.) and their residue effect on fodder maize (*Zea mays*). *Indian Journal of Agriculture Sciences* **74**(7): 359-361.
10. **Patel, H.K., Patel, P.M., Suthar, J.V. and Patel, M.R. 2014.** Yield, quality and post harvest nutrient status of chickpea as influence by application of sulphur and phosphorus management. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publication* **4**: (7).
11. **Kumawat, N., Kumar, R. and Sharma, O. P., 2009.** Nutrient uptake and yield of moong bean *Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek as influenced by organic manure, PSB and phosphorus fertilization. *Environment & Ecology* **27** (4B) 2022-2005.
12. **Sinha, R.K., Valani, D., Chauhan, K., Agarwal, S. 2010.** Embarking on a second green revolution for sustainable agriculture by vermiculture biotechnology using earthworms: Reviving the dreams of sir Charles Darwin. *Journal of Agriculture, Technology and Sustainable Development* **2**: 113-128.
13. **Singh, S. and Kapoor, K. K., 1992.** Effect of inoculation of phosphorus solubilizing microorganism and an arbuscular mycorrhizal fungus on moongbean grown under natural soil condition. *Mycorrhiza* **7**: 249-253.
14. **Singh B. and Pareek, R. G., 2003.** Effect of phosphorus and biofertilizer on growth and yield of moongbean. *Indian j. of pulse res.* **16**: 31-33.
15. **Franco, L.O., Maia, R.C.C., Porto, A.L.F., Messias, A.S., Fukushima, K., Takaki, G.M.C. 2004.** Heavy metal biosorption by chitin and chitosan isolated from *Cunninghamella elegans* (IFM 46109). *Brazilian Journal of Microbiology* **35**(3): 243-247.
16. **Yadav O. S. 2001.** Effect of nitrogen sources and biofertilizer on growth and quality of cowpea. M. Sc. (Ag) thesis, SKRAU, Bikaner, India.
17. **Giaquinta, R. T. and B. Quebedeaux 1980.** Phosphate induced change in assimilate partitioning in soyabean leave during pod filling. *Pl. Physiol.* **65** : 119.

Table 1. Effect of different liquid biofertilizer under varying fertility levels on N, P content and uptake in seed and straw

Treatments	N content (%)		P content (%)		N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		P uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	Seed	Straw	Seed	Straw	Seed	Straw	Seed	Straw
Fertility levels								
F ₀ -Control	3.092	0.972	0.743	0.218	39.82	22.45	9.56	5.05
F ₁ -50%N+75%P ₂ O ₅ +75%K ₂ O+50 % S	3.205	1.011	0.766	0.226	50.75	28.84	12.14	6.46
F ₂ -75%N+85%P ₂ O ₅ +85%K ₂ O+75 % S	3.298	1.035	0.784	0.232	56.17	31.92	13.36	7.16
F ₃ -100% NPKS	3.303	1.038	0.788	0.236	58.78	33.03	14.03	7.52
SEm _±	0.017	0.003	0.004	0.002	0.85	0.39	0.25	0.13
CD (P=0.05)	0.052	0.011	0.013	0.005	2.62	1.21	0.78	0.40
Liquid Biofertilizers								
B ₀ - Control	3.130	1.000	0.750	0.220	42.63	24.53	10.21	5.39
B ₁ - Rhizobium (N-Fixing)	3.225	1.019	0.773	0.229	52.78	29.99	12.64	6.74
B ₂ - PSB+PMM (P-Solublizer & Mobilizer)	3.223	1.014	0.770	0.228	51.08	28.92	12.20	6.49
B ₃ - KMB (K-Mobilizer)	3.220	1.008	0.769	0.227	50.14	28.25	11.97	6.36
B ₄ - Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB	3.244	1.025	0.779	0.233	54.29	30.93	13.02	7.03
B ₅ - SSB (S-Solublizer)	3.218	1.003	0.767	0.226	49.69	27.90	11.84	6.28
B ₆ - Rhizobium + PSB + PMM + KMB + SSB	3.313	1.030	0.787	0.236	59.05	32.88	14.01	7.52
SEm _±	0.021	0.002	0.003	0.001	0.82	0.41	0.20	0.10
CD (P=0.05)	0.058	0.007	0.009	0.004	2.30	1.15	0.55	0.29

Table 2. Interactive effect of different liquid biofertilizer under varying fertility levels on N uptake by seed and straw (kg ha⁻¹)

Treatments	Seed						
	B ₀	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₆
F ₀	37.22	40.88	39.27	39.13	41.37	38.49	42.39
F ₁	44.56	52.43	51.40	50.02	53.04	49.21	54.59
F ₂	43.45	57.83	55.77	54.65	60.56	54.40	66.53
F ₃	45.32	60.00	57.86	56.75	62.20	56.65	72.69
SEm _±	1.64						
CD (P=0.05)	4.59						
	Straw						
F ₀	21.40	23.15	22.22	21.88	23.33	21.58	23.57
F ₁	25.75	29.92	29.19	28.29	30.29	27.73	30.73
F ₂	25.15	33.01	31.68	30.97	34.69	30.65	37.28
F ₃	25.84	33.91	32.60	31.86	35.42	31.65	39.94
SEm _±	0.82						
CD (P=0.05)	2.29						

Table 3. Interactive effect of different liquid biofertilizer under varying fertility levels on P uptake by seed and straw (kg ha⁻¹)

Treatments	Seed						
	B ₀	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₆
F ₀	8.96	9.84	9.43	9.40	9.98	9.22	10.12
F ₁	10.68	12.57	12.29	11.96	12.74	11.74	12.97
F ₂	10.35	13.79	13.26	12.99	14.46	12.91	15.72
F ₃	10.84	14.36	13.81	13.54	14.91	13.49	17.24
SEm _±	0.39						
CD (P=0.05)	1.09						
	Straw						
F ₀	4.69	5.20	4.98	4.92	5.30	4.85	5.38
F ₁	5.62	6.69	6.52	6.34	6.85	6.21	6.99
F ₂	5.50	7.38	7.08	6.95	7.85	6.86	8.49
F ₃	5.73	7.70	7.39	7.25	8.13	7.19	9.23
SEm _±	0.21						
CD (P=0.05)	0.58						